

SOCIAL CLASS OR ETHNIC BACKGROUND? DETERMINANTS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL CAREERS OF ETHNIC MINORITY PUPILS*

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Introduction

Up until the late eighties, research into educational careers was dominated by two themes, i.e. social and gender inequality (Bosker, 1990; Diederer, 1989; De Graaf, 1987; Tesser, 1986). The studies mainly focused on the educational disadvantages of working-class children and girls. Attention for gender inequality in education seems to have recently faded into the background. Since the second half of the eighties however, there has been a strong increase in the interest devoted to ethnic inequality in education (De Jong, 1987; Driessen & Jungbluth, 1994; Eldering, 1989). A discussion has recently started on whether the issue of ethnic inequality is a unique, new phenomenon or can in fact be traced back to the social inequality observed in the past. In other words, it is about whether the disadvantaged position of many ethnic minority pupils¹ can in fact be explained by the same aspects and mechanisms that accounted for the educational disadvantages of children from the Dutch lower socio-economic classes (Driessen, 1993; Van 't Hof & Dronkers, 1993; De Lange & Rupp, 1992)². On the basis of reviews by Meijnen & Riemersma (1992) and Driessen (1995), it appears possible to give an affirmative answer to this question for the time being. This does not alter the fact that various problems have been noted with regard to the research and analyses, which may modify this conclusion.

In recent large-scale, longitudinal studies on educational careers, for example by Statistics Netherlands (CBS) and on Educational Priority Policy cohorts (Driessen & Van der Werf, 1992; Mulder, 1996; Van der Werf, 1995), it has been common to describe an entire year group of pupils and monitor their progress throughout their educational career. In the description of their careers, certain categories of pupils are compared on particular educational position characteristics. The studies focus on differences between Dutch pupils and pupils of foreign descent, which may or may not be combined with differences between pupils from higher and lower social classes. A less common approach examines factors that might influence differences in school careers between various sub-categories *within* the group of pupils of foreign descent. It is evident that there are major differences among newcomers in terms of their educational

position as well as their background characteristics (Driessen, 1990; Driessen, Mulder & Jungbluth, 1995). This article follows this line of thought: we look at a number of background characteristics to see whether they account for differences in educational careers within the group of ethnic minority pupils. More specifically, this article has two aims. First of all, we want to see to what extent differences in educational careers among ethnic minority pupils are caused by factors relating to social class. In addition, we investigate whether characteristics related to ethnic origin could provide a further explanation for these differences in educational careers.

Hypotheses

In trying to explain the differences in educational careers among ethnic groups, one generally starts from two perspectives, the disadvantaged and the immigration perspective (Penninx, 1988; cf. also Dronkers & Kerckhoff, 1990; Roelandt, Martens & Veenman, 1990)³. At the root of the *disadvantaged perspective* lies the equal opportunities idea. According to this outlook, the position a person acquires should be determined by his or her abilities. In this perspective, in principle no distinction is made according to ethnic origin. The big differences in educational position stem from the fact that pupils come from different social classes. For Dutch pupils as well as pupils of foreign descent from lower social classes, the same unfavourable social, educational and material factors (in particular within the family) are responsible for the low educational position.

Social class is the most generally accepted indicator for the disadvantaged perspective (Dronkers, 1989). We therefore expect ethnic minority pupils whose parents have a lower socio-economic position, to have more limited chances of school success than ethnic minority pupils whose parents belong to the higher social classes.

In essence, the *immigration perspective* means that when transferring from one society to another, individuals have to overcome certain cultural and social differences. This involves unfamiliarity with cultural norms and values, with written and unwritten rules, and with the structure of society. Not having a command of the language of the recipient country or access to existing networks is usually also an important problem. This gives rise to a great deal of problems for immigrants trying to achieve social status. It is possible to observe major differences among immigrant groups based on migration history and cultural and linguistic aspects (Dronkers & Kerckhoff, 1990). One assumption is that the degree of disadvantage is related to 'cultural distance' (cf. De Jong, 1987). In due time – once the transitional problems have been solved, – the differences in social position between ethnic minorities are expected to diminish. The same expectation applies to differences in educational position currently being observed.

On the basis of this immigration perspective, we assume that the differences in educational careers among ethnic minority pupils can be explained in part by the number of children per family, which can be seen as an indicator of the financial resources a child gets by birth (De Graaf, 1987). In large ethnic minority families where children have to share a bedroom with brothers or sisters, there is less room to do homework or prepare for tests than in small ethnic minority families. As a result, the educational careers of children from large ethnic minority families are less likely to be a success. In addition, a child from a large family will no doubt receive less support and attention from his parents than a child from a small family, since there is much more competition in large families for the parents' attention. This more limited amount of attention means children have fewer opportunities to talk about school and are less likely to excel; as a result their achievements are lower (cf. Blake, 1989). In the Netherlands, this type of effect has been demonstrated by Van Eijck & De Graaf (1994).

The pupils' length of stay in the Netherlands also plays a role (De Jong, 1987). In general, the length of their stay in the new country has a positive effect on the school achievements of ethnic minority children, i.e. the longer the pupils have been in the Netherlands, the better their school achievements (Mulder, 1996; Roelandt, Martens & Veenman, 1990).

A good command of the Dutch language is another important condition for immigrant pupils to get on well at school (Driessen, 1992). After all, the language at school is Dutch, barring a few exceptions. Dutch is however not only acquired at school in formal educational situations, but also outside school, which will have a favourable effect on school achievements. Thus the more Dutch is spoken at home, the better the achievements at school are likely to be.

Data, operationalization and method

Data

The data analyzed in this article come from the cohort VOCL'89 ('Secondary Education Pupils Cohort 1989')⁴, and pertain to 19,524 pupils from 381 schools who were in the first year of secondary school in the 1989/90 school year and whose educational careers have been monitored ever since. This means that every year, we saw what year and school type the pupils were currently in. As a result, it was not only possible at all times to determine the educational level, but also to see whether pupils had to repeat a year or dropped out, or went on to a higher or lower school type. In addition, achievement tests were administered in year 1 and year 3 (1989/90 and 1991/92). We made use of the data up to and including the 1991/92 school year; the basis was the original sample from 1989/90. On the whole this sample can be seen as representative of all the pupils in the first year of secondary school in 1989/90. It should be noted, however, that at the start of this study the big cities were slightly under-represented at the school level, in

particular Amsterdam and the Hague. In addition, HAVO (Senior General Secondary School) and IBO (Individualized Junior Secondary Vocational School) were slightly under-represented and MAVO (Junior General Secondary School) and LBO (Junior Secondary Vocational School) slightly over-represented at the pupil level. Probably in connection with this, there might have been an under-representation of pupils in socio-ethnic disadvantaged situations. In comparison with the situation in 1989/90, there was virtually no selective drop-out in 1991/92 on the characteristics investigated here. For further information about the cohort design and representativeness, we refer to CBS (1991) and Driessen & Van der Werf (1992a, 1992b, 1994).

The data for this article were obtained from parents, schools and pupils. The parents provided information about family and pupil characteristics by means of a written questionnaire. The school career characteristics were gathered by means of questionnaires and tests at the school and via the pupils.

Operationalization

The first variable is ethnic origin. It is a variable of nominal measurement level. Since we will be making use of linear regression analysis later, we have broken ethnic origin down into a number of dummy variables. The categories used are: Surinam, the Antilles and Moluccas; Morocco; Turkey; Southern Europe; other immigrants (the reference category)⁵. As was mentioned in Note 1, by 'immigrant pupils' we mean pupils who were born abroad or whose parents were born abroad (i.e. not in the Netherlands).

For this article, we have taken a sub-sample of 2,024 pupils from the total sample of the immigrants defined in this manner⁶; the analyses will be performed on this number of pupils. Table 1 shows the numbers per ethnic group.

The social class of the pupils was based on two indicators, the family's occupational and educational level. The occupational level was classified by the CBS (1991) in six categories, which could be considered ordinal. The educational level according to the Standard Education Index (CBS, 1987) also had six

Table 1: Number of pupils per ethnic group

	%	N
Surinam, Antilles, Moluccas	17.8	360
Morocco	16.2	328
Turkey	17.0	345
Southern Europe	7.0	141
other immigrants	42.0	850
total	100.0	2,024

categories. This index might not be entirely suitable for immigrant parents, since the education system in the country of origin might deviate from the Dutch one and the index might not differentiate enough at the bottom end. Since the database does not provide any other possibilities, we are nevertheless forced to use this classification. In the case of one-parent families, the occupational and educational level of that one parent was used, and in the case of two-parent families the highest level of the two parents.

Number of children, length of stay in the Netherlands and the extent to which Dutch is spoken at home were included as intermediating variables. They were operationalized in the following way. The number of children per family speaks for itself. Length of stay was expressed as the number of years a pupil had been in the Netherlands. The extent to which the parents speak Dutch to the pupil at home was a composite variable. Both parents were asked whether they 'almost never', 'occasionally', 'frequently' or 'virtually always' spoke Dutch with their child⁷. Subsequently the replies of both parents were put together – in the case of one-parent families only the answers of the one parent were taken – and put into a scale. Cronbach's α for this scale was .92.

The educational career variables that were analyzed were the recommendation for secondary school given in the final year of primary school (year 8, age 11-12), the language and arithmetic achievement levels measured in year 1 of secondary school and the educational position of pupils three years after the start of the cohort. With this we have access to career information from three phases, the transition from primary to secondary school, the starting position at secondary school in terms of language and arithmetic achievement levels and the educational position after three years of secondary school⁸. The recommendation for secondary school is a variable consisting of nine categories, ranging from IBO (Individualised Junior Secondary Vocational School) up to and including VWO (Pre-University School). The language and arithmetic achievement levels were established with a version of the 'Entrance test' compiled by CITO (National Institute for Educational Measurement) and administered half way through the first school year. The language and arithmetic parts consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions. The scores were expressed in the number of correctly answered items. The last educational career variable, the educational position in school year 3, was determined on the basis of the school year ladder (cf. Bosker, 1990). The point of departure here was that school can be seen as a hierarchical system within which it is possible to achieve a certain 'top'. The position on this ladder is determined as the distance a pupil has to cover to reach this top; in essence it is a scale based on a combination of school type and school year, with an allowance made for pupils who had to repeat a year or dropped out.

Method

We used linear regression analysis to answer the research questions. This multi-variate analysis enabled us to determine the relative importance of the effects of the independent variables on the various educational career incidents. In addition to linear regression analysis, a one-way variance analysis was applied in some preparatory analyses.

Results

Some descriptions

Prior to the main analyses, we present the results of some descriptive analyses related to the variables used in this study. Table 2 shows the mean scores of the background characteristics per category of ethnic origin.

Table 2: Family's educational level, family's occupational level, number of children, length of stay and home language Dutch, by ethnic origin (mean scores)

	total	Sur/Ant/ Mol	Morocco	Turkey	S. Europe	other	Eta ²	N
family's educational level	3.0	3.1	1.7	2.0	2.9	3.8	.36	1,995
family's occupational level	2.7	2.6	1.6	1.7	2.5	3.6	.23	2,007
number of children	3.2	2.9	5.0	3.5	2.7	2.5	.30	1,993
length of stay	11.9	11.9	9.9	11.5	10.9	13.1	.08	2,024
home language Dutch	3.0	3.6	1.9	1.9	2.6	3.6	.47	1,974

It is clear that the Moroccan and Turkish parents had the lowest educational level, followed by parents from Southern Europe, and then Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan parents. On the average, families from the other immigrants category had the highest educational level. Virtually the same applied to the families' occupational level.

The number of children also varied a great deal per country of origin. Moroccan families had the highest birth rate. On the average, the Moroccan pupils came from families with 5 children, followed by the Turkish pupils with an average of 3.5 children per family. For the other countries of origin, the average number of children varied between 2 and 3. As far as length of stay is concerned, there were moderate differences between the countries of origin. The biggest difference was 3.2 years between Moroccans (on the average 9.9 years) and the other immigrants category (on the average 13.1 years). The average length of stay for the entire sample of immigrants was almost 12 years. The last variable in Table 2 is the extent to which Dutch was spoken at home. This variable shows the strongest correlation with ethnic origin in comparison with the other variables in the table

(Eta²=.47). Turkish and Moroccan parents spoke the least Dutch with their children, probably because they had the least command of this language themselves. The Surinamese, Antilleans and Moluccans and the other immigrants, on the other hand, most frequently used Dutch as their home language. As in the case of the educational and occupational level of the family, the Southern Europeans were in the middle.

Table 3 shows the recommendation for secondary school, the language and arithmetic achievement levels, and the educational position in school year 3 broken down according to background characteristics.

As far as the educational level of the parents is concerned, it is evident that the higher the parents' level of education, the higher the scores of their children on the four educational career variables. Immigrant pupils from families where the average educational level of the parents was high received a more favourable recommendation for secondary school, did better at language and arithmetic, and held a higher educational position than immigrant pupils whose parents had a low level of education. The same applied to the effect of the family occupational level on educational career incidents. This correlation is however smaller than the correlation between the educational level of the family and the educational career incidents. With regard to ethnic origin, it is very clear that Moroccan pupils had the lowest scores on the various educational career characteristics; Turkish children did not, for that matter, do a great deal better. On the average, Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils and pupils from Southern Europe received a similar recommendation and also held the same educational position in school year 3. The language and arithmetic achievement levels of the Southern European pupils were however higher than of the pupils of Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan origin. Other immigrants did best, irrespective of the educational career variable.

Social class and ethnic origin

From the results shown in Table 3, it is possible to deduce that the background characteristics social class and ethnic origin influence the educational career differences. Up until now, we have only looked at bi-variate relationships. The question is whether in the multi-variate case, these effects of social class and ethnic origin also exist independently of each other. In order to work this out in more detail, we have carried out a linear regression analysis with as exogenous variables social class, measured on the basis of the family's educational and occupational level, and ethnic origin. The different educational career incidents serve as independent variables in this model. Table 4 shows the non-standardised (b) and the standardised (β) regression coefficients of this analysis⁹.

Table 3: Recommendations for secondary school, language and arithmetic achievement levels and educational position in school year 3, by total sample, families' educational level, families' occupational level and ethnic origin (mean scores)

	recommendations secondary school	language achievements	arithmetic achievements	educational position school year 3
Total sample	4.8	10.2	9.5	5.7
<i>families' educational level</i>				
no primary school	3.8	7.6	7.3	5.1
primary school	4.1	8.8	8.0	5.3
secondary school, lower stage	4.4	9.9	8.8	5.4
secondary school, higher stage	5.3	11.6	11.0	6.0
higher education, first stage	6.1	13.1	12.6	6.5
higher education, second stage	7.3	14.4	14.5	7.3
Eta ²	.22	.20	.18	.20
N	1,847	1,896	1,889	1,995
<i>families' occupational level</i>				
unemployed	4.1	8.7	7.8	5.3
manual labourers	4.2	9.6	8.9	5.4
(small) shopkeepers	5.2	10.4	11.0	5.9
lower level employees	5.2	11.6	10.7	5.9
middle level employees	5.7	11.8	11.6	6.2
higher level employees	6.6	13.5	13.1	6.7
Eta ²	.17	.14	.13	.13
N	1,858	1,908	1,901	2,007
<i>ethnic origin</i>				
Surinam, Antilles, Moluccas	4.8	10.1	9.0	5.6
Morocco	3.8	7.9	7.4	5.1
Turkey	4.0	8.4	7.9	5.2
Southern Europe	4.8	10.5	10.0	5.7
other immigrants	5.3	11.7	11.1	6.0
Eta ²	.09	.12	.09	.08
N	1,872	1,921	1,914	2,024

Table 4 shows that the indicators to measure social class had a positive effect on the various educational career incidents. The families' educational level had relatively the strongest effect (b ranges between .31 and .33). In terms of content, this means that immigrant pupils whose parents had a high level of education received a higher recommendation for secondary school, did better at language and arithmetic, and held a higher educational position than immigrant pupils

Table 4: Parameter estimates of the model with social class characteristics. Equation 1: secondary school recommendation; equation 2: language achievement levels; equation 3: arithmetic achievement levels; equation 4: educational position school year 3; equation 5: educational position school year 3 corrected for other educational career variables (N=1,708)

	1		2		3		4		5	
	b	β	b	β	b	β	b	β	b	β
intercept	2.83**		7.32**		5.58**		4.59**		3.01**	
families' educational level	.47**	.32**	.94**	.31**	1.10**	.31**	.30**	.33**	.05*	.05*
families' occupational level	.19**	.17**	.24**	.10**	.36**	.13**	.09**	.12**	-.01	-.01
ethnic origin:#										
– Surinam, Antilles, Moluccas	.06	.01	-.71**	-.06**	-.83**	-.06**	-.08	-.02	-.05	-.01
– Morocco	-.09	-.02	-1.21**	-.10**	-.50	-.03	-.02	-.00	.09	.02
– Turkey	-.04	-.01	-.96**	-.08**	-.24	-.02	-.03	-.01	.03	.01
– Southern Europe	.11	.01	-.14	-.01	.14	.01	.08	.02	.04	.01
sec. school recommendation									.39**	.62**
language achievement levels									.04**	.14**
arithmetic achievement levels									.03**	.12**
adj. R ²	.21		.21		.19		.18		.68	

reference category: other immigrants

* p<.05; ** p<.01

whose parents had less schooling. In addition the families' occupational level influenced the four different educational career variables. The higher the occupational level of the parents, the greater the success during the educational career. Furthermore, the ethnic origin of a pupil had an autonomous influence on academic achievement. For language, the Moroccan pupils performed the worst of all, followed by the Turkish children; Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils did slightly better. The language achievement levels of pupils from Southern Europe and from the other immigrants group were highest and did not differ significantly from each other. The results on the arithmetic test were worst for the Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils. Compared with the reference group, other immigrants, who achieved the best test results, they were the only ethnic group to achieve significantly lower on the arithmetic test.

Finally, in the far right-hand column of Table 4, if we take into account the educational career variables, the effects of social class and ethnic origin on the educational position in school year 3 were minimized. Only the families' educational level still had a modest influence ($\beta=.05$) on the educational position. Furthermore, the recommendation for secondary school at the end of primary school was a very good indication of a pupil's educational position after three years of secondary school.

Number of children, length of stay and home language Dutch

By adding the variables number of children, length of stay and home language Dutch to the regression equations analyzed above, we can see to what extent migration characteristics provided an additional explanation for differences in educational careers between immigrant pupils. Table 5 shows the estimated regression coefficients for these equations.

Table 5: Parameter estimates of the model with social class and migration characteristics. Equation 1: secondary school recommendation; equation 2: language achievement levels; equation 3: arithmetic achievement levels; equation 4: educational position school year 3; equation 5: educational position school year 3 corrected for other educational career variables (N=1,708)

	1		2		3		4		5	
	b	β								
intercept	2.78**		6.28**		4.63**		4.65**		3.16**	
families' educational level	.48**	.33**	.96**	.32**	1.12**	.32**	.32**	.35**	.06**	.06**
families' occupational level	.19**	.17**	.22**	.09**	.36**	.13**	.09**	.13**	-.00	-.00
ethnic origin.#										
- Surinam, Antilles, Moluccas	.10	.02	-.56*	-.05*	-.74*	-.06*	-.06	-.02	-.05	-.01
- Morocco	-.09	-.01	-.89*	-.07*	-.59	-.04	-.14	-.04	-.05	-.01
- Turkey	-.12	-.02	-.93**	-.08**	-.41	-.03	-.17	-.05	-.07	-.02
- Southern Europe	.09	.01	-.01	-.00	.18	.01	.02	.00	-.02	-.00
number of children	-.02	-.01	-.06	-.02	.07	.02	.01	.02	.02	.03
length of stay	.03*	.05*	.12**	.10**	.09**	.07**	.02*	.05*	-.00	-.01
home language Dutch	-.09	-.05	-.09	-.02	-.15	-.03	-.11**	-.09**	-.06**	-.06**
sec. school recommendation									.39**	.62**
language achievement levels									.04**	.14**
arithmetic achievement levels									.03**	.12**
adj. R ²	.21		.22		.19		.18		.68	

reference category: other immigrants

* p<.05; ** p<.01

Table 5 shows that migration characteristics only had a very limited effect on educational career incidents. The number of children did not have a significant effect on the educational career of immigrant pupils at all, while the extent to which Dutch was spoken at home only influenced the educational position. The effect was contrary to the expectations: the more often parents spoke Dutch with their children at home, the lower the educational position after three years of secondary school. The explanation for this negative effect is still unclear, but it could have something to do with the selective item non-response mentioned in Note 7. The third intermediating variable, length of stay in the Netherlands, is the only predictor that met with our expectations: it had a positive effect on all

four educational career variables. The recommendation for secondary school was higher, the language and arithmetic achievement levels were higher and the educational position in school year 3 was more favourable, the longer immigrant pupils had been in the Netherlands.

If we compare the effects of social class and ethnic origin from Table 5 with those of Table 4, it is striking that they did not diminish as a result of the migration characteristics being added. The effects of social class remained unchanged and the influence of the dummies for ethnic origin did not change appreciably either. In terms of content, this means that ethnic and cultural factors such as the number of children, length of stay in the Netherlands and home language Dutch are not mechanisms that can account for the relationship between social class and ethnic origin and educational career characteristics. The families' educational level and to a lesser extent, occupational level and ethnic origin continue to be the most important predictors for differences in the educational careers of immigrant pupils.

If we take into account the other educational career variables (regression equation 5), we see once again that it is only the families' educational level and earlier educational career incidents that significantly influenced the educational position in school year 3. Furthermore home language Dutch had an autonomous effect on the educational position in the third school year. Once again pupils whose parents spoke Dutch with them held a lower educational position after three years of secondary education.

Interactions with ethnic origin

In the previous analyses, we started from the assumption that social class and migration characteristics carry the same amount of weight for each of the different immigrant groups in explaining differences in educational careers. The question is whether this assumption is correct; the effects can differ for various sub-categories. The parents' educational level will often have a different meaning in one country of origin than in another. It is also possible that, as a result of differences in migration history, the influence of the length of stay in the Netherlands on educational careers differs per ethnic group. The same may be the case for the number of children and the extent to which Dutch is spoken at home. A high recommendation for secondary school can have different consequences for one category of immigrant pupils than another. In determining good school results for language and arithmetic, the weight one attaches to them may also vary per category of immigrant. In order to investigate these possible differences, we have added interactions with ethnic origin to the earlier regression equations we analyzed, so we can compare the effects of the background characteristics on the educational career variables per immigrant group. Only the significant interaction terms have been included in the definitive model (see Table 6).

Table 6: Parameter estimates of the model with social class and migration characteristics including interactions. Equation 1: secondary school recommendation; equation 2: language achievement levels; equation 3: arithmetic achievement levels^a; equation 4: educational position school year 3; equation 5: educational position school year 3 corrected for the other educational career variables^b (N=1,708)

	1		2		3		4		5	
	b	β	b	β	b	β	b	β	b	β
intercept	2.75**		6.27**		4.63**		4.72**		3.16**	
families' educational level	.53**	.36**	.95**	.31**	1.12**	.32**	.34**	.38**	.06**	.06**
families' occupational level	.18**	.15**	.23**	.10**	.36**	.13**	.11**	.16**	-.00	-.00
ethnic origin: [#]										
- Surinam, Antilles, Moluccas	.09	.02	-.60*	-.05*	-.74*	-.06*	-.62	-.19	-.05	-.01
- Morocco	.28	.05	.46	.04	-.59	-.04	.27	.07	-.05	-.01
- Turkey	-.99*	-.17*	-2.69**	-.23**	-.41	-.03	-.65*	-.18*	-.07	-.02
- Southern Europe	2.23**	.27**	1.74	.10	.18	.01	.02	.00	-.02	-.00
number of children	-.01	-.01	-.05	-.02	.07	.02	.01	.01	.02	.03
length of stay	.00	.01	.09**	.08**	.09**	.07**	.01	.03	-.00	-.01
home language Dutch	-.02	-.01	.02	.00	-.15	-.03	-.14**	-.13**	-.06**	-.06**
sec. school recommendation									.39**	.62**
language achievement levels									.04**	.14**
arithmetic achievement levels									.03**	.12**
<i>interactions with ethnic origin</i>										
S/A/M x occupational level							-.13**	-.13**		
S/A/M x home language Dutch							.26**	.29**		
Morocco x educational level	-.56**	-.19**					-.22*	-.11*		
Morocco x length of stay	.07*	.13*								
Turkey x length of stay	.08**	.19**	.16*	.17*			.04*	.15*		
S. Europe x number of children	-.38*	-.14*	-.64*	-.11*						
S. Europe x home language Dutch	-.41*	-.15*								
adj. R ²	.23		.22		.19		.19		.68	

^a none of the interactions are significant; effects are equal to the estimates of equation 3 Table 5

^b none of the interactions are significant; effects are equal to the estimates of equation 5 Table 5

[#] reference category: other immigrants

* p<.05; ** p<.01

Table 6 shows that the effect of the parents' educational level on the educational position of the pupils was significantly smaller for Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils than for the other immigrants reference group (b=-.13). The extent to which Dutch was spoken at home had fewer negative effects on the position in secondary school for pupils from the former Dutch colonies than for the other immigrants category. In addition, the effect of the families' educational level on the recommendation for secondary school and the educational position was different for Moroccan pupils than for the reference group. The educational

effect for Moroccan children was respectively .56 and .22 smaller. In addition, the length of stay in the Netherlands was more important for Moroccan and Turkish pupils than for the reference group. For Moroccans, this was only the case for the recommendation for secondary school, but for Turkish children the length of stay not only had a stronger positive influence on the recommendation for secondary school, but also on the language achievement levels and the educational position. For Southern Europeans, the negative effect of the number of children on the recommendation for secondary school and the language achievement levels was stronger than for the other immigrants (respectively -.38 and -.64). Almost the same applied to home language Dutch: the extent to which Dutch was spoken at home had more negative effects for the recommendation for secondary school for Southern European pupils than for the other immigrants reference group.

Conclusions

In this article we have focused on the educational careers of pupils of foreign descent. The aim was to find out to what extent social class and migration characteristics could account for differences in educational careers. We measured social class on the basis of the educational and occupational level of the family, and ethnic origin on the basis of the country of birth of the pupil and his/her parents. The analyses show that social class and ethnic origin were both determinants for the educational careers of immigrant pupils. The effect of the families' educational level appeared to be most significant in the educational career incidents we analyzed. Immigrant pupils whose parents completed a higher level of education, were given higher recommendations for secondary school, did better at language and arithmetic, and in time held a higher educational position than immigrant pupils whose parents had hardly had any education, regardless of their occupational level and ethnic origin. A similar conclusion to the one reached in relation to educational level also applies to occupational level.

If social class was kept constant, ethnic origin was only a determining factor for the language and arithmetic achievement levels. Moroccan, Turkish and – somewhat surprisingly – Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils had by far the lowest achievement levels as far as Dutch language skills were concerned. As far as arithmetic was concerned, Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils had significantly lower test scores than the other immigrants reference group.

The second part of the analyses addressed the extent to which migration characteristics such as the number of children, the length of stay and the extent to which Dutch was spoken at home provided an additional explanation for the differences in educational careers once social class characteristics were taken into consideration. From the analyses in which we added the relevant intermedi-

ating variables to the original model, it was clear that they hardly added anything extra. Statements to the effect that differences in educational careers between immigrant children diminish if differences in the length of stay in the Netherlands, the variation in the number of children and the extent to which parents speak Dutch with their children at home are taken into account, were not confirmed by the analysis we carried out. Social class – in particular the families' educational level – and to a lesser extent ethnic origin continue to be the most important predictors for differences in educational careers between immigrant children.

By comparing the four most important categories of immigrant pupils with the group of other immigrants, we have come to the conclusion that the educational careers of the various ethnic groups differed considerably on a number of points. The effect of the families' occupational level on the educational position achieved was more limited for Surinamese, Antillean and Moluccan pupils than for the other immigrants. In addition, among Moroccans the recommendation for secondary school and the educational position after three years of secondary school was less strongly determined by the parents' educational level than among the reference group other immigrants. Furthermore, the effects of the number of children, the length of stay and Dutch as the home language sometimes deviated from those of the group other immigrants on the various school career incidents.

In view of these findings, it can be concluded that the differences in school success among ethnic minority pupils can be explained for the most part by the same factors that play a role in the educational disadvantage for some Dutch pupils. For ethnic minority pupils, social class is also the most important factor for a successful educational career. Specific characteristics of immigrants – as a result of their different migration histories and diverse cultural backgrounds – hardly provide any further explanation, nor do they explain part of the relationship between social class and a successful educational career. The disadvantaged perspective therefore provides a better explanation for the differences in educational careers between immigrant pupils than the immigration perspective.

NOTES

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1. By 'ethnic minority pupils' we mean pupils who were born abroad or whose parents were born abroad (i.e. not in the Netherlands); the other pupils we label 'Dutch'. 'Ethnic groups' include the ethnic minority as well as the Dutch pupils.
2. This discussion raises the question posed by more qualitatively-oriented researchers as to whether or not 'traditional' educational career research is in fact suitable and able to expose the underlying aspects and mechanisms in an adequate manner (Pels & Veenman, 1996; Teunissen & Matthijssen, 1996) but that is beside the point here.
3. Fase (1994) distinguishes an autonomous ethnic factor. One should approach this point bearing

in mind the various possibilities for adequately dealing with the opportunities and impediments on the education market. He mentions three domains within this context: the domain of interpersonal relationships, of the school as an institution, and of socialisation differences between the school and the family. He is not totally convincing, though. After all, these types of aspects can also be explained from the disadvantaged perspective. In more concrete terms, the barriers for Dutch working-class children in these domains are similar to those for children of foreign descent.

4. The data used for this article were collected and made available by Statistics Netherlands (CBS).
5. Although the composition of the reference category 'other immigrants' is fairly heterogeneous, this is not relevant for the comparison of the effects. The distances between the various immigrant groups, which is what it is all about here, are not dependent on the choice of the reference category. That does not alter the fact that when it comes to a content-related interpretation of the differences between the reference category and the other distinguished groups, this might become less clear.
6. It should also be noted that by purely focusing the analyses on the immigrant pupils, and excluding indigenous pupils, the problem of a sample which is skewed in reference to ethnic origin is avoided (cf. Latuheru & Hessels, 1996). By doing so, we also avoid the possible negative effects of multi-collinearity (cf. Driessen (1995) and the discussion between Dronkers & Van 't Hof (1993) and Veenman (1993). Table 2 shows that the correlation between ethnic origin and the two indicators used to measure social background amounts at the very most to .60 (i.e. .36).
7. The question here is whether or not one could speak of 'selective item non-response' in this case. Because if one asks parents in Dutch whether they speak Dutch at home, one will get very little response from parents who do not have a good command of the Dutch language.
8. Strictly speaking, the latter is not entirely correct, because at the start of the cohort in school year 1 the entire year group was included, including the pupils who had already repeated school year 1. Analyses have however shown that extra effects on selected career characteristics such as repeating a year and dropping out are insignificant (cf. Driessen, 1994).
9. As a result of the list-wise deletion option in the regression analyses, the number of respondents was lower than the original 2,024 pupils. This was largely related to the absence of data on recommendations and tests. The first was due to the fact that the primary schools did not always pass their recommendations on to the secondary schools; the latter was due to the fact that not all of the pupils completed the tests due to absence. After correction, this did not distort the results.

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